

Quantifying the Degradation of Human Decision-Making Under Time Pressure Through the Self-Information of Chess

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Abstract

Though it is well established that time pressure has detrimental effects on human cognition, its relative effects across different levels of competency remain largely unquantified. To address this gap, we extend Claude Shannon’s work in information theory to the game of chess. To quantify the quality of human decision-making in a chess game, we calculate the probability of all legal moves in a given position from engine evaluations using a softmax function. Then, we sum the Shannon information of each played move in a single game to obtain the game’s total surprisal. By applying this framework to a large dataset of 22,500 chess games from the lichess.org Open Database, our results show that time pressure does not affect individuals of different skill levels uniformly. Highly skilled players effectively utilize additional time to improve decision quality, decreasing surprisal, whereas less skilled players exhibit poor baseline decision quality, high surprisal, which does not improve with additional time. These findings highlight the importance of distinguishing between skill-based and time-based limiting factors in any cognitive performance-based context, such as timed test-taking.

1 Introduction

The game of chess provides extensive data for studying human behavior using information theory, with its finite space holding near-infinite possibilities [8]. Studying how individuals navigate this near-infinite landscape under time constraints provides quantifiable insight into the effects of time pressure on human computation [2].

Claude Shannon, often regarded as the “Father of the Information Age,” laid the foundations of information theory, which revolutionized numerous fields, including cryptography, physics, and biology [9, 6]. Central to his theory is the concept of surprisal, a measure of how “unexpected” an event is. This concept of surprisal can be extended to cognitive science, where in the context of this research, greater surprisal correlates with poorer decision quality.

While it is well established that time pressure has detrimental effects on human cognition [4], quantifying these effects remains difficult. Furthermore, its relative effects across different knowledge/skill levels remain largely unknown.

This research aims to remedy both these problems in human decision-making through the lens of chess. Chess offers quantifiable decision-making, fixed-time play, and sufficient information content, making it an ideal medium for analyzing the effects of time pressure on human decision quality. This paper argues that as time becomes less of a limiting factor, competency becomes the primary limiting factor in performance; those with high levels of competency are more affected by time pressure.

2 Data Selection & Categorization

2.1 Skill Groups

Skill groups are defined using Elo, a rating system to quantify the relative skill of players. We define a game's Elo μ to be the average Elo between both players, white and black.

$$\mu = \frac{\text{Elo}_{\text{white}} + \text{Elo}_{\text{black}}}{2} \quad (1)$$

Games will be sorted into one of three skill groups based on their respective game Elo. These skill groups are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \textbf{Beginner} & \mu < 1400 \\ \textbf{Intermediate} & 1400 \leq \mu < 2000 \\ \textbf{Expert} & \mu \geq 2000 \end{aligned}$$

Additionally, any games with an Elo difference $\Delta\mu$ of > 150 will be excluded from the data analysis to avoid skewing the results due to large skill imbalances.

$$\Delta\mu = |\text{Elo}_{\text{white}} - \text{Elo}_{\text{black}}| \quad (2)$$

2.2 Time Controls

We define a game's estimated time duration in seconds by Lichess's definition [3], which is as follows:

$$\tau = (\text{initial time in seconds}) + 40(\text{increment}) \quad (3)$$

Games will be categorized into three time-control groups based on their estimated duration. The time controls selected for analysis are Bullet, Rapid, and Classical, with Bullet providing the least time per player and Classical the most. Any game not under one of these time control definitions will be excluded. The time controls are defined as follows:

Bullet $29 < \tau \leq 179$
Rapid $479 < \tau \leq 1499$
Classical $\tau \geq 1500$

Note that the gap between Bullet and Rapid is due to the fact Blitz $179 < \tau \leq 479$ was excluded to maximize contrast.

3 Methodology

3.1 Evaluation Framework

Let L represent the set of all legal moves in a given board state. For each move in the set $\forall x \in L$, a centipawn value E will be assigned to its corresponding move using the Stockfish chess engine, where E_1 is the evaluation of the best move, and E_i is the evaluation of the move played. Evaluations where a mate is found will be evaluated as +20000 centipawns [10]. Note that evaluations will always be from the relative perspective of the side whose turn it is (positive if winning, negative if losing).

Example position demonstrating the evaluation framework, with a table representing all legal moves with the UCI move x and evaluation E represented as (x, E) .

3.2 Probability Framework

We assume that the probability of a move follows an exponential relationship with the relative evaluations of all the other legal moves, which is expressed in a softmax function. Barthelemy (2025) introduced a temperature parameter Δ_0 to scale probabilities based on skill level, $\Delta_0 = 100$ for beginners, $\Delta_0 = 50$ for intermediates, and $\Delta_0 = 10$ for experts[1]. While Barthelemy (2025) uses distinct temperature parameters for each skill group, we fix $\Delta_0 = 50$ for all skill groups, to later allow direct comparison between skill groups.

$$p_i = \frac{e^{E_i/\Delta_0}}{\sum_{x \in L} e^{E_x/\Delta_0}}$$

A softmax function calculates the probability of a move from a set of all legal moves L in a position, where E_i is the evaluation E of the played move, and E_x is the evaluation E of the move x in the set L .

3.3 Surprisal Framework

To quantify human decision quality, we utilize Shannon self-information, where the surprisal $h(x)$ of an outcome x measured in bits [5, 7] is defined as:

$$h(x) = \log_2 \frac{1}{P(x)}$$

In the context of chess, we define p_i as the probability p of the move at ply i , allowing the self-information I_i of that move to be expressed as:

$$I_i = -\log_2(p_i)$$

The total surprisal C of a game can be expressed as the summation of the self-information of each move, where the upper limit n represents the total number of plies in the game, such that:

$$C = \sum_{i=1}^n -\log_2(p_i)$$

To calculate the average surprisal \bar{C} per move across all games in a given time control, let N represent the total number of games, C_i represent the total information of game i , and n_i represent the total number of plies in game i . The average surprisal per move is then:

$$\bar{C}_{\text{per move}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{C_i}{n_i}$$

Note that this average is not weighted by game length.

4 Procedure

We used the October 2025 monthly dump from the lichess.org open database, totaling 29.9 GB and containing 91,549,148 games, as the primary source of chess game data. The compressed file was extracted to a single PGN file containing all chess games.

Using Go, we developed a PGN database extractor to parse and organize games from the PGN file into nine separate CSV files based on time control and skill group (e.g., Rapid-Intermediate, Classical-Expert, etc), as defined in the Data Selection & Categorization section. Additionally, the analytical dataset excluded games with Elo differences $\Delta\mu$ exceeding 150, games not under any of the defined time control definitions, and games with ply < 40 or > 80 .

Once the chess game data had been cleaned and organized, we developed a Python script to calculate the total surprisal of each game, along with the average surprisal per move for each skill group, with results saved for visualization using Matplotlib. Stockfish 17.1 (Linux x64, AVX2) was the chess engine used for position evaluation. Additionally, percent differences were calculated between all time controls to test for negligibility.

To view and download our illustrative demo code, see PGN Database Extractor and Chess Surprisal.

5 Results

For the purposes of this study, we treat differences less than 1% as effectively negligible given the sample size.

Expert players exhibited the greatest total surprisal in Bullet games, followed by Rapid, and finally Classical.

Figure 1: Average total surprisal of games within the Expert group. Data is plotted by total game length (ply) across three time controls (Bullet, Rapid, Classical), with each line representing 2,500 games.

Intermediate players exhibited the greatest total surprisal in Bullet games, while Rapid and Classical followed, showing a negligible difference from each other.

Figure 2: Average total surprisal of games within the Intermediate group. Data is plotted by total game length (ply) across three time controls (Bullet, Rapid, Classical), with each line representing 2,500 games.

Beginner players exhibited a negligible difference between Rapid, and Classical, with Bullet exhibiting a slightly lower average total surprisal.

Figure 3: Average total surprisal of games within the Beginner group. Data is plotted by total game length (ply) across three time controls (Bullet, Rapid, Classical), with each line representing 2,500 games.

Skill Group	Time Control	Average Surprisal per Move (bits)
Beginner	Classical	4.8513
Beginner	Rapid	4.8115
Beginner	Bullet	4.482
Intermediate	Bullet	4.2664
Expert	Bullet	3.9605
Intermediate	Classical	3.8213
Intermediate	Rapid	3.7907
Expert	Rapid	3.3129
Expert	Classical	3.0965

Table 1: Average surprisal per move by skill group and time control, in descending order by surprisal.

6 Discussion

Preliminary analysis of Figures 1–3 indicates that all three graphs exhibit a natural positive correlation as the number of moves increases, reflecting the fact that more information is available as the number of moves increases. Additionally, we can interpret skill groups (Expert, Intermediate, and Beginner) as an individual’s competency, and total surprisal (the degree of deviation between a human’s moves and the best moves) as their performance, where greater surprisal corresponds to worse performance [2].

Expert group: A negative correlation is observed between time allotted and total surprisal across all three time controls. This suggests that expert players effectively use additional time to improve their performance, though the performance increase may plateau beyond a certain point as allotted time increases.

Intermediate group: a negative correlation is observed between time allotted and total surprisal between Bullet and Rapid time controls; however, a negligible difference is observed between Rapid and Classical. This suggests that intermediate players effectively use additional time to improve their performance, but plateau beyond 25 minutes, as skill becomes the dominant limiting factor.

Beginner group: No correlation is observed between time allotted and total surprisal between Classical and Rapid. However, Bullet games exhibited slightly lower surprisal. We attribute this to a combination of game-simplification and a survivorship bias. Due to the extreme time constraints, the beginner players likely resorted to playing simpler moves to save time. Additionally, since the analysis did not include games with a ply < 40 , games with extremely high surprisal were likely to end early due to resignation or checkmate. This suggests that beginner players are unable to effectively use additional time to improve their performance because skill is the dominant limiting factor.

Comparative analysis: Comparing the average surprisal per move from Table 1 provides information on the relative effects that time pressure and skill have on decision quality (surprisal). According to the data from Table 1, Intermediates performed 12.55% better in Rapid than Bullet, while Experts performed 19.55% better in Rapid than Bullet and 6.99% better in Classical than Rapid.

These findings can be extended to similar time-limited evaluations based on objective factors, such as timed test taking. If we interpret a player’s skill in chess as someone’s knowledge of test material, we can predict that an individual with a strong grasp of the test content would have time as their dominant limiting factor, while an individual with a weak grasp of the test content would have their own knowledge as the dominant limiting factor. This can help develop test-taking strategies by prioritizing mastery of the subject matter rather than attributing limited performance to time management.

For future research, a temperature parameter should be derived from an analysis of a large dataset of games across all skill levels specifically for this research to more accurately model surprisals values.

Additionally, centipawn values for positions where a mate is found should be scaled by the number of moves to the mate. For example, a mate in one should have a larger centipawn value than a mate in four, which is more likely to be overlooked by players.

In conclusion, this research demonstrates that time pressure does not affect individuals of different skill levels uniformly. Highly skilled players can effectively use additional time to improve decision quality, while less skilled players are more constrained by their competence. These findings highlight the importance of differentiating between skill-based and time-based limiting factors in any performance-based context.

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